

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

HEADSTART D7.3. Data Management Plan

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PARTNERS

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

The table herein presents the typical abbreviations used in WP7 – Management and Coordination:

Abbreviation	Meaning
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAD	Connected Automated Driving
CAV	Connected and Autonomous Vehicles
Dx.y	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Office
DoA	Description of the Action
DoW	Description of the Work
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEADSTART	Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport
H2020	Horizon 2020
IM	Innovation Manager
IMS	Innovation Management System
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KET	Key Enabling Technologies
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NCAP	New Car Assessment Programme
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
PM	Person Month
QM	Quality Manager
RP	Reporting Period
SC	Steering Committee
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

The objective of the deliverable

As part of the HEADSTART project, WP7 has the objective of coordinating and managing the project. A close coordination must be maintained along all the partners and their activities in order to ensure the achievement of the project's objectives.

This deliverable describes the Data Management Plan. It is linked mainly to T7.4 'Data management' with the support of T7.2 'Technical management'. This report provides the Data Management Plan in order to outline the planning of the data management activities for the pool of data that will be collected within the project. The document explains how the research data collected or generated will be handled during and after a research project.

The objective of this deliverable is to present the plan for the overall management of data in the project and the correct and adequate handling of data that is of a personal nature, which must be protected, or requires specific treatment from an ethical perspective. These activities are under the lead of the Data Officer (Seán Gaines from Vicomtech). Within this task, the HEADSTART Data Management Plan (DMP) has been defined and will be followed for datasets captured or processed within the project according to the guidelines published by the European Commission, and the integration of data from open Data Sets from the scientific community, and data provided under condition by industrial partners. The DMP will be compliant with the new GDPR for datasets captured or processed within the project according to the guidelines published by the European Commission.

This document provides initial guidelines that define simple and practical pointers during the implementation and validation stages of the project, support compliance on underlying legal obligations and promote the adoption of best data management practices. The document will also detail potential issues of ethical, rather than legal or technical, importance. Additionally, it describes the effective integration of data into a project, create data within a project, and make available data external to a project, consider at an early stage such data will be managed must be given early in the project, and continuously during its execution. The primary concerns will be the management, sharing and creation of data. The DMP establishes a plan in an attempt satisfy the EC's expectations for data management, which are as follows:

- Any Horizon 2020 project is invited to submit a DMP as an early project deliverable if it is relevant to their research.
- All projects submitting a research proposal to 'Research and Innovation Actions' and 'Innovation Actions' are required to include a short outline of their general data management policy.
- All projects which are successfully funded under the Pilot on Open Research Data are expected to produce an initial DMP deliverable within the first six months of the project
- Each of the required points for the DMP should be addressed on a dataset-by-dataset basis.
- List file types, formats, and the reuse potential for other researchers.
- Where possible use existing metadata standards which will allow for potential integration with other datasets.
- Explain how the data will be shared, and the level of access to be provided (and why).
- Use a repository service to deposit the data and where possible make it and the underlying metadata accessible to third parties, free of charge.
- Arrange backup and storage procedures which are most suited to the partners and nature of your project.

The dissemination level of D7.3 is public. Participants leading or contributing to the preparation of deliverables must read and apply all the procedures related to the preparation of the deliverables.

1 Introduction

1.1 The HEADSTART project in a nutshell

HEADSTART (Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport) is a European project funded under Horizon 2020 Framework Programme within the call ART-01-2018 (the type: Research and Innovation action). HEADSTART is represented by the consortium of 17 partners that are top automotive manufacturers, suppliers, test labs and researchers.

HEADSTART will define testing and validation procedures of CAD functions including:

- its key enabling technologies (i.e. communication, cyber-security, positioning),
- cross-links of all test instances such as simulation, proving grounds and real-world field tests, and
- safety and security performance validation according to the needs of key user groups (technology developers, consumer testing and type approval).

HEADSTART has 3 ACTION PILLARS mapped with end users of the project results:

- Testing and validation (development): e.g. OEMs,
- Assessment - Consumer testing: e.g. Euro NCAP,
- Certification (type approval): e.g. Type approval authorities & Technical services.

FIGURE 1: HEADSTART OBJECTIVES

The five objectives of the HEADSTART project comprise (Figure 1):

- OBJECTIVE 1: IDENTIFY - Create a dynamic catalogue of existing methods, procedures and tools for testing, validation and certification considering multi-stakeholder requirements.
- OBJECTIVE 2: HARMONISE - Harmonisation of existing testing and validation approaches taking into account other industries and domains.
- OBJECTIVE 3: DEFINE & DEVELOP - Define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD building upon existing initiatives.
- OBJECTIVE 4: DEMONSTRATE - Demonstrate the developed methodologies, procedures and tools through the testing of relevant CAD use cases.
- OBJECTIVE 5: REACH CONSENSUS - Reach consensus by creating and managing an expert network of CAD testing to promote adoption of the project results considering multi-stakeholder needs.

Like other European projects, HEADSTART is organized following a WP structure (Figure 2). The main objective for WP7 (the WP covered extensively in this document) is to ensure the successful execution of the project through a professional and effective management and coordination, with the achievement of the project objectives. WP7 contains all the technical and administration related project management and will deal with all Data Management and Innovation Management related issues. The objective of WP8 is to ensure compliance with the 'ethics requirements' set out in this work package.

FIGURE 2: HEADSTART WP STRUCTURE

The expected project results are as follows:

TABLE 1: EXPECTED HEADSTART RESULTS AND CORRESPONDING TRL

Advancement of TRL in the HEADSTART Project	Initial TRL	Final TRL
Scenario description to include KETs	3 - 4 depending on KETs	6
Cyber-security test methods and tools	3	5-6
V2X communications test methods and tools	4	6
Positioning test methods and tools	5	7
Target platforms for CAD testing	6	7
CAD Testing protocols	5	7-8

1.2 Data management task

The results of the HEADSTART project are ultimately for the benefit of society. However, the focus of the research goals raises immediate and justifiable concerns around the protection of personal data, ethics and in guaranteeing citizens fundamental rights and freedoms, as well as needing to ensure that the project results are not misused. As part of WP7, T7.4 'Data management' has the objective to provide the overall management of data in the project and the correct and adequate handling of data that is of a personal nature, which must be protected, or requires specific treatment from an ethical perspective. Within this task, the HEADSTART Data Management Plan (DMP) has been defined and will be followed for datasets captured or processed within the project according to the guidelines published by the European Commission, and the integration of data form open Data Sets form the scientific community, and data provided under condition by industrial partners. The DMP will be compliant with the new GDPR for datasets captured or processed within the project according to the guidelines published by the European Commission.

This task will define simple and practical pointers during the implementation and validation stages of the project, support compliance on underlying legal obligations and promote the adoption of best data management practices. The task will also deal with potential issues of ethical, rather than legal or technical, importance. The primary concerns will be the management, sharing and creation of data.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The report is structured into chapters as follows. Section 1 describes an instruction to the HEADSTART project, as well as to the data management activities in the action. Section 2 introduces the main concepts within this Data Management Plan, including some background on the topic; the types of data; the specificities of personal data, describing activities for protection and securing of personal data, personal data collection, processing, and re-use, the appointment of a Data Controller, and compliance with the GDPR; finally, roles and responsibilities are detailed.

Section 3 focuses on data description, including a general overview, the HEADSTART datasets, versioning and referencing, as well as data classification. Section 4 describes the FAIR data management principles, i.e. making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. This chapter also describes the participation of HEADSTART in the open access to research data initiative.

Finally, Section 5 addresses the necessity for allocation of resources related to data management (and open access), Section 6 describes data security and repositories for storage and Section 7 related ethical issues, including data acquisition and processing under informed consent and an initial policy on incidental findings. Some final remarks and comments are summarised in Section 8

2 Data Management

2.1 Background

The European Commission has long recognized that research data is as important as any project publications or result. Furthermore, the value of data as a tangible resource fit for exploitation is continuously better recognized by the market, research communities, society and industry as a whole. This leads to a need for a form of structured approach to the used of research data within and applied research project that balances the need of all actors from a myriad of perspectives.

Open access to scientific publications is mandatory for all scientific publications resulting from Horizon 2020 funded projects. In addition, projects must also aim the availability of research data needed to validate the results presented in the published scientific publications, known as "underlying data". This must also be balanced with commercial concerns and, more importantly, both European and National Data Protection legislation. The previous body of legislation was a patchwork of legislation under 95/94/EC due to transpositions to national law of the same directive. Furthermore, these transpositions may vary from region to region within a member state depending on the type of organization processing personal data and/or the level of autonomy a region possesses.

In order to effectively integrate data into a project, create data within a project, and make available data external to a project, such data management must be given consideration early in the project, and continuously during its execution. The primary concerns are the management, sharing and creation of data.

Any research project DMP should describe what data the project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved.

The HEADSTART project will, a priori, participate in the EC's Pilot on Research Data, and to this end it will make available relevant, but not all, data in a research data repository. The possible benefits from data sharing will include, perhaps, creating a community around the dataset, where publications allow validation of results and in which the data may be used to accelerate future research. This will foster collaboration and advances in research, citing the dataset and thus making project results more visible with a greater impact.

To maximise the extent of the data dissemination, HEADSTART will implement provisions for third parties to access, exploit and reproduce the data, including the information necessary for validating the project's results.

This document establishes a plan in an attempt satisfy the EC's expectations for data management, which are as follows:

- Any Horizon 2020 project is invited to submit a DMP as an early project deliverable if it is relevant to their research.
- All projects submitting a research proposal to 'Research and Innovation Actions' and 'Innovation Actions' are required to include a short outline of their general data management policy.
- All projects which are successfully funded under the Pilot on Open Research Data are expected to produce an initial DMP deliverable within the first six months of the project
- Each of the required points for the DMP should be addressed on a dataset-by-dataset basis.
- List file types, formats, and the reuse potential for other researchers.
- Where possible use existing metadata standards which will allow for potential integration with other datasets.
- Explain how your data will be shared, and the level of access to be provided (and why).
- Use a repository service to deposit your data and where possible make it and the underlying metadata accessible to third parties, free of charge.
- Arrange backup and storage procedures which are most suited to the partners and nature of your project.

- Complete more detailed DMPs at regular intervals throughout your project when changes occur or as a minimum in the run up to mid-term and final reviews.

The DMP addresses the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the project participants with regard to all datasets. Hence, it also establishes some procedural mechanisms for participants with the responsibilities as Data Controllers and Processors. For each dataset, the following aspects will be considered:

- **Overview of Policies:** with respect to relevant bordering international initiatives and programmes.
- **Roles:** identifying the different participants, the roles played and their responsibilities.
- **Data Set Reference and Name:** Identifier for the data set to be produced.
- **Data Set Description:** description of the data that will be generated or collected, its origin (in case it is collected), nature, scale, to whom it could be useful, and whether it underpins a scientific publication. Information on the existence (or not) of similar data and the possibilities for integration and reuse.
- **Standards and Meta Data:** reference to existing suitable standards within the field. If these do not exist, an outline on how and what metadata will be created.
- **Data Infrastructure:** details of data production and provision assets.
- **Data Sharing:** description of how data can be shared, including access procedures, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and definition of whether access will be completely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating in particular the type of repository (institutional, standard repository in the field, etc.). In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy, security, export restrictions, competitive interest).
- **Archiving and Preservation (Including Storage and Backup):** description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, what is its approximated end volume, what the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered. This includes organised deletion of data and backups after the preservation period is finished so that personal data is not stored longer than necessary.

In addition, any project that produces, collects or processes research data should also take into account that data used to produce the research results of the project should be as much as reasonably possible:

- **Discoverable:** identifiable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. Digital Object Identifier).
- **Accessible:** the data and associated software are produced and/or used in the project accessible and in what modalities, scope, licenses (e.g. licensing framework for research and education, embargo periods, commercial exploitation, etc.).
- **Assessable and Intelligible:** covering the capacity of third parties of accessing and using data with a shortest as possible learning curve.
- **Usable Beyond the Original Purpose for Which it was Collected:** easing the application of the data in other domains or sectors.
- **Interoperable to Specific Quality Standards:** Following data exchange between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (e.g. adhering to standards for data annotation, data exchange, compliant with available software applications, and allowing re-combinations with different datasets from different origins).

2.2 Data Types

There are four main types of research data that will be considered during the HEADSTART project:

- **Observational data:** captured in real time, typically cannot be reproduced exactly. For HEADSTART this could be GPS, license plate and human facial features from driving data.
- **Experimental data:** from labs and equipment, can often be reproduced but may be expensive to do so. For HEADSTART, this could be testing ground data, including identity and behaviour of the test driver.
- **Simulation data:** from models, can typically be reproduced if the input data is known. For HEADSTART, this will involve for example simulation of the vehicle under test in a virtual environment, including driving performance of the vehicle.
- **Derived or compiled data:** after data mining or statistical analysis has been done, can be reproduced if analysis is documented. For HEADSTART, this may involve test analysis results and safety validation conclusions.
- **Secondary use data:** since HEADSTART will collaborate with other projects for evaluating use cases, data from other projects will be needed. This can be of any of the four types mentioned above.

2.3 Personal Data

This section concerns research which involves processing of personal data, regardless of the method used (e.g. interviews, questionnaires, direct online retrieval etc.). In the context of HEADSTART, 'personal data' means information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number (e.g. vehicle registration plate), location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person (art. 2(a) EU General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR).

In particular, we expect the following personal data for HEADSTART:

1. Observational data: location, license plate and human faces of drivers on the public road;
2. Experimental data: identity and behaviour of test drivers;
3. Simulation data: identity and behaviour of human drivers if included in the simulation, e.g. in case of usability testing;
4. Derived or compiled data: demonstration videos showing drivers

2.3.1 Activities for Protection and Securing of Personal Data

As Data Manager of the HEADSTART project, Mr. Gaines shall ensure the consortium guarantees the treatment of personal data generated during the project. This will be done via a set of development directives and methodologies. To ensure that secure systems development principles are integrated from the inception of the project, best practices will be issues to RTD staff in the HEADSTART project to ensure the project applies adequate database encryption and secure systems techniques.

Furthermore, the directives and mandates will also integrate the technical requirements of European data protection regulation. Partners will be required to have adequate security measures in place, both technical (firewalls, access controls, access audits, etc.) and operational (training, incidence reporting, etc.).

From a legal perspective, Privacy Impact Assessments will be carried out if required, the adequate classification of personal data types will be done for each data set, retention and rectifications policies will be followed. Furthermore, as will be detailed in the following sections, it will be critical to clearly identify data processors and owners and provide a contractual framework for the exchange and sharing of data amongst project partners, if necessary.

When necessary, a methodology must be applied for obfuscation, anonymization or pseudo anonymization of personal data at source, or near to source, when recorded by sensors (including minimisation techniques in sensor setup itself, e.g. camera pan and tilt angles when facing the exterior of a vehicle). For example, visual identification cues (faces, license plates etc.) will be blurred from video data and, origin and destination data will be erased or dissociated in GNSS localisation Data.

Finally, Deliverable D3.5 Specification of test procedures for selected Use Cases will include a section with detail information on the procedures for data collection, use and destruction as well as how the data anonymization process is going to be developed from the captured data specific to the Use Case and Study in question.

2.3.2 Personal Data Collection, Processing, and Re-use

HEADSTART will involve personal data collection and processing by a limited number of partners. It will also involve observation of participants arising from Data Sets and involves further processing of previously collected personal data (i.e. secondary use). Every project partner is subject to the GDPR and to national data protection laws, including for example data transfer restriction and also the prior mandates of the Article 29 Working Group. The following key principles (without considering exemptions) will apply:

1. Data must be processed fairly, lawfully and only for the purpose for which it was collected and further processed;
2. Data cannot be disclosed without authorisation unless there is an overriding act of law or legitimate grounds to do so;
3. Subject to certain exemptions, individuals have a right to access the information relating to them and to ask for correction of inaccurate data;
4. Information cannot be transferred beyond the EEA boundaries without consent or adoption of other adequate protection measures;
5. Organisations are usually required to register or notify the processing of personal data unless the data processing is simplistic or a data protection officer has been appointed;
6. Organisation must have adequate security measures in place.
7. The HEADSTART consortium exercise a principal of minimum resort to notification exemptions afforded under national laws.

2.3.3 Appointment of Data Controller

The project consortium has identified and appointed a role of Data Controller for project. The Data Controller will be HEADSTART's Data Manager: VICOMTECH. Sean Gaines will be the point of contact for Data Protection issue and will coordinate the actions required to liaise between different partners and their respective Data protection agencies.

2.3.4 Compliance with GDPR

The 'data minimisation' principle will apply to the HEADSTART project, and we will limit the processing of data to the strictly relevant and limited to the purposes of the project. Under these rules, personal data must be processed in accordance with certain principles and conditions that aim to limit the negative impact on the persons concerned and ensure fairness, transparency and accountability of the data processing, data quality and confidentiality.

This implies the following main obligations: data processing should be subject to appropriate safeguards, data should wherever possible be processed in anonymised or pseudonymised form, data processing is subject to free and fully informed consent of the persons concerned, data processing must not be performed in secret and research participants must be made aware that they take part in a research project and be informed of their rights and the potential risks that the data processing may bring, data may be processed only if it is really adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for your research.

One of the best ways how to avoid or limit data protection issues for the HEADSTART project is to use anonymised or pseudonymised data. Therefore, techniques for the dissociation and anonymisation of personal data of the subjects generated during trials will be applied when required. The objective will be to comply with the GDPR and to ensure that the techniques applied are rolled into the final results of the project for their eventual exploitation. VICOM as Data Manager will declare the types of data being collected, the nature of the file used to store the data, the retention policy and security control as part of its routine reporting of research projects, updating the Data Management plan as necessary.

All the described measures will guarantee that our research complies with ethical principles, applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, the GDPR, national data protection laws and other relevant legislation).

Other documents that will be considered during the project include the following:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1)
- Guidelines on Consent under Regulation 2016/679 (wp259rev.01), Article 29 Working Party
- Guidelines on Transparency under Regulation 2016/679 (wp260rev.01), Article 29 Working Party
- Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679(wp251rev.01), Article 29 Working Party
- Council of Europe Modernised Convention for the Protection of Individuals with Regard to the Processing of Personal Data, CM/Inf (2018)15-final
- Handbook on European data protection law (2018 edition), European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, European Court of Human Rights, European Data Protection supervisor
- Data transfers outside the EU - International data transfers using model contracts

2.4 Roles and responsibilities

Since the HEADSTART project will imply processing of personal data, detailed information will be provided with regards to the technical and organisational measures to safeguard the rights of the research participants. For

those organisations that must appoint a data protection officer under the GDPR, the DPO will be involved in the project directly and will disclose the contact details to the research participants. Moreover, details of the project-specific data protection policy will be finalised.

The responsibilities of the DPO will be in line with Article 39 of the GDPR and will include, at a minimum, the following:

1. Advise data controllers and processors within the HEADSTART project on the processing of personal data, training of researchers and assignment of responsibilities.
2. Provide support on the performance and tracking of Impact Assessments.
3. Assist in risk assessment of personal data processing.
4. Cooperate with any national or European supervisory authority and act as contact point for the project with such authorities.

3 Data description

3.1 General description

This section provides an explanation of the different types of data sets to be produced or collected in the HEADSTART project, which have not been yet identified at this stage of the project. As the nature and extent of these data sets will evolve during the project, more detailed descriptions will be provided in following versions of the DMP. The descriptions of the different data sets, including their reference, file format, standards, methodologies and metadata and repository to be used are given below.

3.2 Datasets

Within the project a multitude of datasets that cover several file formats, data types, scenarios, sizes, etc. will be produced. Each partner will contribute with either private or publicly available datasets, providing the following details for each of them:

TABLE 2 DATASET INFORMATION TO BE PROVIDED

Dataset name	NAME
Dataset reference	HEADSTART_WPX_TX.X_XX Each data set will have a reference that will be generated by the combination of the name of the project, the Work Package and Task in which it is generated and the reference number.
Data set owner	Owner organisation(s) and contact person(s)
Source	Dataset source (specify reuse if applicable)
Use Case (s)	Related UC in the HEADSTART project.
Data set description and relation to the objectives of the project	Each data set will have a full data description explaining the data provenance, origin and usefulness. Reference may be made to existing data that could be reused.
Data Quality	Quality parameters related to the dataset.
Format	All the format that defines data.
Size	Size of the dataset.
Technology	Technology set-up, sensor, etc. used in the creation of the dataset.
Derived Data	Data extracted from the created dataset.
Reuse of existing data	If applicable

Dataset name	NAME
Data sharing	<p>Explanation of the sharing policies related to the data set between the next options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open: Open for public disposal • Embargo: It will become public when the embargo period applied by the publisher is over. In case it is categorised as embargo the end date of the embargo period must be written in DD/MM/YYYY format. • Conditional: Only available under special conditions, to be arranged between stakeholders. • Restricted: Only for project internal use. Each data set must have its distribution license. Provide information about personal data and mention if the data is anonymised.
Archiving and preservation	The preservation guarantee and the data storage during and after the project (databases, institutional repositories, public repositories...).

3.3 Versioning and referencing

Both raw captured and metadata processed information may be included in datasets. In each phase the dataset will be generated/acquired and process different datasets targeting the same information, but from different infrastructures. For each dataset the corresponding Data Controller will assure that the above information is defined:

- Contact Name - telephone and email contact details
- Date of First Version - Date the first version was completed
- Date of Last Update - Date it was last changed

Concerning the dataset versioning, folders structure and filenames, to help people to find the data, the title/reference will include who created or contributed to the data, date of creation and under what conditions it can be accessed. Thus, each Structure is formed as follows:

- DATE: ISO8601 Representation. Create date
- TIME: ISO8601 Representation with Zulu offset to CET
- TITLE: Data set title
- OWNER: Author using email address
- PARTNER: Partner short name
- WP-TASK: DoA Linked Task, e.g. WP3T2.2
- MAJOR: Major Version Number "XX."
- MINOR: Minor Version Number ".YY"
- DIST: DoA Distribution level

3.4 Data classification

For data that does not fall within the scope of personal data in the GDPR two broad categories will be applied and treated as follows:

Confidential data that needs protection

There are several different kinds of commercial data that might need protection. When signing contracts for provision of such data, it is advisable to discuss the foreseen protection level, so that both parties can agree on a suitable level of protection. Several things affect the protection level. A way to categorise the commercial data could be:

TABLE 3: CATEGORISATION OF COMMERCIAL DATA

Data Category	Access	Ownership
Open	Open for all or certain project partners	Jointly or Uniquely owned by partners
Closed	Confidential data open to all or certain project partners during the project. Available on a per case basis approved by the owner.	Data provider
Proprietary	Confidential data that is never or rarely shared, as the commercial value or risk of the data is too high to share.	Data provider

The closed data could be made more open e.g. by aggregating the data, producing a non-sensitive level of information, thus avoiding commercially harmful misuse of the original data.

Non-sensitive data

The definition of non-sensitive is data that is completely anonymised and does not include any confidential elements. This means that no personal identifiable data is available in the dataset (i.e. video, images or GPS traces). If video is included in the dataset, any field or test participant must be anonymised (e.g. obfuscated) to ensure the personal anonymity, but also other objects that can be used to identify a person (e.g. registration plates, commercial signing).

4 FAIR Data

The data that will be generated during and after the project should be 'FAIR', that is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. These requirements allow a variety of implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard, or implementation solution.

The FAIR principles were generated to improve the practices for data management and data-curation, and FAIR aims to describe the principles in order to be applied to a wide range of data management purposes, whether it is data collection or data management of larger research projects regardless of scientific disciplines.

With the endorsement of the FAIR principles by H2020 and their implementation in the guidelines for H2020, The FAIR principles serve as a template for lifecycle data management and ensure that the most important components for lifecycle are covered. This is intended as an implementation of the FAIR concept ('spirit') rather than a strict technical implementation of the FAIR principles ('literal').

4.1 Making data findable

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

- The data sets will have very rich metadata to facilitate the findability.
- All the data sets will have a Digital Object Identifiers provided by the public repository (e.g. ZENODO).
- The reference used for the data set will follow this format: HEADSTART_WPX_TX.X_XX
- The data sets will be made available using public repositories

4.2 Making data accessible

To be able to make data accessible the following requirements have to be met:

1. (meta)data will be retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol;
2. the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable;
3. the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary; and
4. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

The retention period of data and information collected, stored and processed for the dataset will be determined during the last 12 months of the project. After the end of HEADSTART, unless otherwise decided by the consortium members, the database functionality will remain the same as during the project execution.

A record will track entities reusing the HEADSTART datasets by means of a data sharing agreements. These third parties will not have default rights for re-distribution or of publishing the dataset partially or totally requiring the reference to the dataset in any publication or derived product. Nor shall the party have rights to commercialise the data set or any derivative works of the data set. Any potential users that wish to obtain access to the data will be under the DMP conditions respecting the sensitivity of data. Here, a nondisclosure agreement and license agreement would give sufficient protection for confidential and sensitive data.

Any potential user that wishes to access the data would be required to:

1. Submit a "request" to the data manager from the HEADSTART consortium. This request will contain:
 - full name
 - organisation and department

- email address
 - description of intended use
2. After reviewing the request. If the data manager approves it or discusses modifications with the requester. The user will receive an email with a special link to verify the email address.
 3. Then the user is asked to agree to and sign the following terms of access: [RESEARCHER_FULLNAME] (the "Researcher") has requested permission to use a specific HEADSTART dataset (the "Dataset"). In exchange for such permission, Researcher hereby agrees to the following terms and conditions:
 - a) Researcher shall use the Data set only for non-commercial research and educational purposes.
 - b) Controller makes no representations or warranties regarding the Dataset, including but not limited to warranties of non-infringement or fitness for a particular purpose.
 - c) Researcher accepts full responsibility for his or her use of the Dataset and shall defend and indemnify supplying party, including their employees, trustees, officers and agents, against any and all claims arising from Researcher's use of the Dataset, including but not limited to Researcher's use of any copies of copyrighted dataset that he or she may create from the Dataset.
 - d) Researcher may provide research associates and colleagues with access to the Dataset provided that they first agree to be bound by these terms and conditions.
 - e) Controller reserves the right to terminate Researcher's access to the Data set at any time and without notice.
 - f) If Researcher is employed by a for-profit, commercial entity, Researcher's employer shall also be bound by these terms and conditions, and Researcher hereby represents that he or she is fully authorised to enter into this agreement on behalf of such employer.
 - g) The laws and jurisdiction of the data supplying party's country (and if necessary, region) shall apply to all disputes under this agreement.

4.3 Interoperability of data

To be able to exchange data, interoperability is pursued, and the following requirements will be met:

1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation;
2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles; and
3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

4.4 Reusing data

To be able to reuse developed data, data sets should meet the following requirements:

1. meta(data) richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes;
2. (meta)data released with a clear and accessible data usage license;
3. (meta)data associated with detailed provenance; and
4. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

The conditions for reusing data have been described in section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..**

4.5 Open access to research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in HEADSTART, beneficiaries will:

- deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate the following:
 - the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible;
 - other data, including associated metadata, as specified in this Data Management Plan;
- provide information, via the repository, about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating them.

As an exception, the HEADSTART beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data if the achievement of the action's main objective would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan will be updated to explain the reasons for not giving access.

5 Allocation of resources

All partners that intend to publish scientific papers have a minimum budget for conference, open access fees, and other dissemination costs (on top of travel and expenses). These budget allocations should allow covering (at least partially) the costs of complying with the open data requirements of the project.

Within the last 12 months of the project, an assessment on which data should be preserved on the long term will be made. As part of this assessment, an estimation on the associated costs will be made. VICOM as the partner in charge of Data Management in HEADSTART, will coordinate this assessment.

6 Data security and repositories

The HEADSTART project has implemented a shared repository for information and documents. This shared repository uses BOX service and it is protected by user and password so that only members that have been granted permission can access it. For long term preservation and curation of data, before the end of the project, an appropriate data repository (or repositories) will be identified and used. Re3data.org, ZENODO and OpenAIRE guidelines on how to select such repositories will be followed^{1 2}.

Because the data managed is not confidential and not related to personal data or trade secrets due to our data protection measures and it will be anonymised, the risks to data security are minimum but still managed according to ISO 27001. The following security requirements have been identified and are presented:

¹ <http://www.re3data.org/>

² <https://www.openaire.eu/opendatapilot-repository>

- **Access Control (Authorisation):** HEADSTART dataset repository must be capable of controlling the level of access that each user has depending on their role. There must be appropriate mechanisms to define and enforce such access control (e.g. firewalls, file systems permissions, secure log-in, password renewal) including physical control. This is provided by the IT department of the dataset maintainer or by the dataset repository technology itself.
- **Authentication:** It must guarantee that the system being accessed is the intended one and that the user is who claims to be. During the project, the partners will have access using a private password. Once the datasets become public, an e-mail based authentication mechanism will grant access.
- **Non-Repudiation:** To ensure the capability to prevent users from denying that data files were accessed, altered or deleted, auditing processes must be implemented. This is provided by the IT department of the dataset maintainer or by the dataset repository technology itself.
- **Data Confidentiality:** Within the scope of the project, the protection of information from unauthorized access and disclosure must be preserved by restricting per-user access and encrypting the information during transmission and also during storage. After the defined retention period expires, ensure information erasure/destruction. This is provided by the IT department of the dataset maintainer or by the dataset repository technology itself.
- **Communication Security:** Communication only flows through encrypted communication channels. This is provided by the IT department of the dataset maintainer or by the dataset repository technology itself.
- **Data Integrity:** HEADSTART must protect data from unauthorized, uncontrolled, or accidental alteration during storage or transmission with the use of checksum values, hash functions and digital signatures. This is provided by the IT department of the dataset maintainer or by the dataset repository technology itself.
- **Availability:** Back-up mechanisms are a desirable property, mainly to avoid Denial of Service (DoS) attacks. This is provided by the IT department of the dataset maintainer or by the dataset repository technology itself.

7 Ethical aspects

The research carried out in the framework of HEADSTART will comply with ethical principles and all the applicable international, EU and national law. We commit to ensuring respect for people and for human dignity and fair distribution of the benefits and burden of research, and that we will protect the values, rights and interests of the research participants.

The guiding principles at the heart of the HEADSTART approach are the highest ethical standards, the protection of privacy and the validity of data and its accurate representation. In adhering to these principles and remaining cognisant of concerns that arise in the Work Plan, HEADSTART will take the following steps, in addition to those detailed above, toward addressing these:

- Compliance with the policy recommendations made in the Social Impact Expert Working Group EC DG ENTR Report (2012);
- The availability of partners or external advisers with Ethics, Privacy and Legal expertise to all HEADSTART project staff members at the outset of the project and throughout;
- Assurance that Privacy by Design, Ethics, Legal and Societal Impact requirements are included as research and development mandates integrated into the HEADSTART project plan in compliance with GDPR Article 25.
- Test and evaluation of research results will be carried out under the principle of informed consent.

Further consideration shall be given to the following relevant regulation, decisions and guidelines. The following EU regulations are recognised to be relevant for the project:

- The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (especially articles 3, 7, 8, and 25).
- Directive 2001/20/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use.
- Convention for the Protection of Individuals with Regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data (Convention Nr. 108).
- WMA Declaration of Helsinki (especially articles 13, 20, 21, 22, 23 and 24, 25).
- Convention of the Council of Europe on Human Rights and Biomedicine signed in Oviedo on 4 April 1997.
- CIOMS - International Ethical Guidelines for Biomedical Research Involving Human Subjects.
- Code of Nuremberg (Article 10).
- Ethics and EU funded research Council Decision 1513/2002/EC on FP6 (e.g. article 3).

All testing should follow Ethical procedures and Sex and Gender aspects. This includes signing in an information sheet and consent form in an accessible format. Informed consent is understood by the partners as an on-going process rather than a level of legal protection. It is not intended to be a one-time act of having a participant sign a form. Informed consent is designed to inform research subjects about the purpose, risks, potential benefits and alternatives to the research that allows people to make a decision about whether or not to participate based on their own goals and values. This exchange of such information should occur at enrolment and throughout the study.

Finally, when conducting observations, surveys, interviews or focus groups where personal information is gathered and stored, we will pay attention to privacy aspects, data protection, data management, and the health and safety of participants.

7.1 Data acquisition and processing under informed consent

HEADSTART will give sufficient advice on exactly which information must be provided to test participants and estimate which arrangements (insurance, exceptional licenses, etc.) are necessary. Detailed knowledge on the experimental setup and the systems to be evaluated is required. In order to conclude a contract/ letter of agreement with test participants, such knowledge on the exact test design and testing procedure is will be provided.

In order to obtain a valid consent from the driver to log the data and allow for safe participation in possible FOTs (Field Operational Tests), naturalistic driving test or physical testing, information on the testing procedure and setup must be comprehensive. The participants do not need to understand the underlying technology in detail but do need to understand the implications of the technology for them so that they can take informed responsibility. This will make the provision of information necessary on which kind of data is being logged in the first place and who will have access. Testing in simulators will be given the same consideration as FOTs or physical tests.

In case a FOT or naturalistic driving test is taken out under real-life traffic conditions and without further surveillance, a great amount of information on safe use is needed. In this case (real-life traffic, no surveillance and no immediately obtainable support), the accurate information as is typically given in a driver's manual will serve as good guidance of what should be provided in a briefing. Thereby, reasonably foreseeable misuse must be taken into account also. The information should be provided in a way that the least informed test-participant, who is therefore most exposed to a danger, can drive safely.

Personal briefing, presentations on how to handle a system under certain conditions or the training of drivers with the possibility to experience the functioning and ask questions are legally sufficient as well. The possibility to ask questions at any time later during a FOT or naturalistic driving project will be provided.

As HEADSTART works with partner projects that develop functionality and perform tests, many of these responsibilities will be under the partner project. However, HEADSTART will set up additional testing where these responsibilities are clearly for the HEADSTART team.

A special issue in the context of briefing is system limitations. System limitations are those features of a system that are not a defect but still lead to wrong information or an erroneous intervention due to a lack of overall system intelligence.

In case a FOT, naturalistic driving study or physical test is conducted to evaluate a pre-production system, possible malfunctions will usually have to be taken into account too. Most important in case of malfunctions will again be to give test participants all the information necessary. That is first of all to provide the information, that a malfunction can occur and instruct thoroughly how to deal with the resulting situations. If technically feasible, recognisability of malfunctions should be made possible. In most cases it will be sufficient to provide for the possibility to switch off the system and thus ensure safety. Even this might not be necessary as long as the malfunction will not impair safe travelling (movement) at all. In case of intervening systems, however, much depends on the period of time available for a reaction of the user.

It is legally required that the driver knows which data is being logged. It should also be pointed out; which conclusions can be drawn from the data available (as far as possibly foreseeable) and this should involve other

data sources and their combination (including external sources that can be resorted to). The meaning of anonymisation and pseudonymisation as well as any other measures to achieve data privacy should be described too. In case of de-personalisation of data is possible and intended, it must be pointed out at which point of the data handling process this is realised.

Based on the provision that data acquisition and processing is generally prohibited, the most important exception from this rule for FOTs, naturalistic driving studies and physical tests is the consent of the person concerned. For any consent given in terms of data acquisition, processing or use, the person concerned must:

- Make this statement in written form (unless certain circumstances – e.g. conclusion of a contract by means of electronic questionnaires over the internet, etc. – make any other form necessary),
- The consequences must be clarified (intended purpose of acquisition/ processing/ use), if consent is not given,
- The consent must even be specially highlighted, if the consent to data acquisition/processing/ use is issued together with other statements (consent to the use, etc. of data concerning health – which might be of interest for FOTs and naturalistic driving studies – will call for a special (separate) consent in this respect)
- Consent must always be given voluntarily.

As sample informed consent form is included in Annex I. Hard copies of signed forms will be stored securely by the project coordinator or test manager. D3.5 Specification of test procedures for selected UC will include a section describing the user selection and test participation procedures and consent.

Data collected may only be processed for the same purpose it has been collected. However, the act comprises a number of exceptions to this rule. As far as (possibly) relevant for a FOT, naturalistic driving study, simulation study or physical test, acquisition, processing and use of data is not limited to the same purpose when:

- The person concerned gives his/ her consent to further use
- The purpose of further use is criminal prosecution (the same will apply in case of an administrative offence) or
- The purpose of further use is scientific research that – from an objective point of view – outweighs the individual interest in data privacy of the person concerned and the purpose of scientific research cannot be achieved otherwise (or only by applying disproportionate effort).

The general principle for data acquisition is that data must be collected openly for the person concerned (and not otherwise). As far as data acquisition is taken out by a public body, this is only possible to such an extent as necessary to fulfil the legitimate tasks. The relevant limitations are:

- Specified in the contract/ letter of agreement on which data acquisition is based
- Restricted to explicit consent
- No more personal data shall be collected and saved than is really necessary to fulfil the purpose in question. A priori, it is preferred that the human subjects in the project will be members of the research staff in the project and therefore employees or agents of the project beneficiaries.

7.2 Policy on incidental findings

An issue of increasing importance in research which involves human beings is the matter of “*incidental findings*”. Incidental findings have been defined as observations of potential significance unexpectedly discovered in research participants and unrelated to the purpose of the study or research. This issue primarily occurs in health-

related research but may occur in other psychological research settings, including those related to Human Factors. Findings such as these have potential implications for a participant's wellbeing, as well as for researchers and the possibility of an incidental finding thus raises issues of a researcher's ability to properly communicate unexpected abnormal findings to the research participant and other designated parties. This issue raises ethical, legal, and regulatory concerns and calls for careful consideration by researchers. The challenges of Incidental Finding raise questions such as:

- What general standards and guidelines should govern the handling of incidental findings in human participant research?
- What kinds of incidental findings should a researcher consider? In many kinds of research, an incidental finding may be exceedingly unlikely?
- In situations in which incidental findings are possible, what represents a significant incidental finding requiring follow-up with a research participant or what threshold should apply for disclosure to a research participant of an incidental finding?
- If disclosure is warranted, who should disclose the incidental finding and what should be the scope, form, and time frame for disclosure?
- Should an ethics review body allow researchers to decline responsibility for detecting and communicating incidental findings, based on ethical, practical, and financial considerations?

Although no general consensus yet exists or prevails on how to handle incidental findings in research, there is empirical evidence supporting an obligation on researchers to address the possibility of discovering incidental findings in their protocols and communications with ethics or review boards, and in their consent forms and communications with research participants. Researchers should establish a mechanism for handling incidental findings and communicate that to research participants. Categorisation and protocols for management and communicating incidental findings should consider:

- Transparency: Research participants, in general, want to know what their research on human factors shows. Appropriate feedback should be given whilst also ensuring privacy and minimising risk.
- Resources: In addition to regulatory requirements for carrying out research, further burden should be avoided. The research purpose must clearly differentiate to research participants the goal of the research and the limit to diagnostic possibilities or scope of incidental findings and their potential relevance.
- Lack of evidence on some key areas: In many research areas there is a lack of ethical guidance and or information to inform practice on the incidental findings and how intervention may benefit the participant.
- Ethics committees: Variation in how ethics committees interpret, understand or are aware of issues related to incidental findings in research.
- Flexibility: One size does not fit all; research goals differ; populations differ; researchers' backgrounds differ. The approach to incidental findings must be flexible to adapt to the peculiarities of the research.
- Evolving field: The technology, aspects of rights of the individual, legal framework, skills and awareness of researchers and availability of tools to support management of incidental findings in research centres are all evolving. Guidance should be flexible and responsive to this change.

8 Conclusion and Next Steps

The content of the presented deliverable is intended to provide an overview on the data management plan of the HEADSTART project in order to ensure that the project is executed successfully.

The objective of this deliverable is to present the plan for the overall management of data in the project and the correct and adequate handling of data that is of a personal nature, which must be protected, or requires specific treatment from an ethical perspective. The HEADSTART Data Management Plan (DMP) has been defined and will be followed for datasets captured or processed within the project according to the guidelines published by the European Commission, and the integration of data from open Data Sets from the scientific community, and data provided under condition by industrial partners. The DMP is compliant with the new GDPR for datasets captured or processed within the project according to the guidelines published by the European Commission.

This document provides initial guidelines that define simple and practical pointers during the implementation and validation stages of the project, support compliance on underlying legal obligations and promote the adoption of best data management practices. The document also details potential issues of ethical importance. This DMP will be updated during the course of the project for the effective integration, creation and FAIR management of data.

Finally, other aspects related to data management will be considered during the execution of the project, such as the use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management, the Metadata Standards Directory provided by the Research Data Alliance, which can be searched for discipline-specific standards and associated tools, as well as other useful tools including online platforms for making individual scientific observations available.

9 Annex I Informed consent form sample

Title of the project: HEADSTART – HARMONISED EUROPEAN SOLUTIONS FOR TESTING AUTOMATED ROAD TRANSPORT

Coordinator: Álvaro Arrúe, IDIADA

Principal Investigator at local level: _____

Institution conducting the tests at local level: _____

Funding: European Union (grant number H2020 - **824309**)

Duration: 2018-2021

Name of participant: _____

Contact data (e-mail, telephone or others): _____

The study described in this text is a part of the research project “HEADSTART”.

1 Introduction

You have been invited to participate in a research study. Before you decide to participate, please read this consent report carefully. Ask all questions you may have to be sure you understand all procedures of the study.

2 Aim of the Study

The HEADSTART project will define testing and validation procedures of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD) functions including its key enabling technologies (i.e. communications, cyber-security, positioning) by cross-linking of all test instances such as simulation, proving ground and real-world field tests to validate safety and security performance.

The purpose of the study is:

- a) To evaluate the functionality of the HEADSTART research technologies in a simulated environment, or, within a controlled environment.
- b) To identify what are the main needs of potential users of such technology
- c) To test partial and final prototypes.

3 Participants in the Study

The participation in the study is voluntary. Participants may withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

The end users’ groups at which this project is aimed are:

1. Able bodied adult (18 years of age or older) in possession of a clean driver's license
2. Project researchers and staff participating on a voluntary basis that comply with the conditions of 1 above
3. Professional test drivers linked to the project partners who's routinely evaluate new automotive technologies.

4 Risk and Limitations

(The participant will be provided with a written statement of potential risks, limitations of the prototypes and protocol for action in the event of failure before tests begin. The will also be given a full briefing by the project staff).

5 Incidental Findings

Although the purpose of the research is the testing and evaluation of CAD technologies, and therefore Human Factors, there is a remote possibility that in the analysis of the research data an incidental finding relating the physical or physiological health of the participant may occur. In this event the participant will be informed of the finding in confidence and as a private person unless there is an explicit indication by the participant they do not wish to be informed.

- I do not wish to be informed of any incidental findings.

6 Privacy and Confidentiality

Any data of a personal nature recorded by the project will be properly dissociated or anonymised and stored securely.

When a person freely agrees to participate in the research, they receive a code-number, and from that moment on all personal data are under that code. Therefore, the analysis of the results will be anonymous, that is no one will know who the data belongs to. The information will be processed during the analysis of the data obtained and will appear in the project deliverables - but again, only in a way that will not allow anybody identification of from whom we received the information assuring in every moment compliance with applicable legislation:

Applicable National Legislation:

(INCLUDE HERE NAME AND NUMBER OF SPECIFIC NATIONAL LEGISLATION)

Applicable European Legislation:

- The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679 regulation on data protection and privacy for all individuals within the European Union (EU) and the European Economic Area (EEA).

The authorisation for the use and access of the information for the aim of research is completely voluntary. This authorisation will apply until the end of the study unless you withdraw it beforehand. In this case we will cease using your data and destroy the same.

If you decide to withdraw your consent later on, we ask you to contact the principal investigator of this study and let him or her know that you are withdrawing from the study.

The Principal Investigator can be contacted under the following address:

(INCLUDE HERE NAME AND CONTACT ADDRESS OF PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR)

From the moment of your withdrawal, your data will not be newly processed in any further phases of the research project. However, it will not be possible to alter already existing published documents or completed project deliverables.

7 Confirmation

Note: Your participation in the study is possible only if you sign a stand-alone consent form that would authorise us to use your personal information and the information on your visual capabilities. If you do not wish to do so, please do not take part in this study.

I have read the information stated in this consent report or it has been adequately explained to me. All my questions on this study and my participation have been answered.

Tick one of the following:

- I read all the information in this form.
- The information in this form was read to me by:
 - All questions I had were answered by:

I authorise the use and dissemination of my answers to the aforementioned entities and for the above-mentioned purposes. The signing of this consent report does not imply the renunciation to any legal right. I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study carried out by (INCLUDE HERE HEADSTART PARTNER CONDUCTING NATIONAL TESTS) and other members of the "HEADSTART" project.

I understand that I am entitled to and will be given a copy of this signed Consent Form.

Name and Surname of participant:

Date:

Signature of participant:

Name and Surname of the researcher:

Date:

Signature of the researcher: